

Metal Complexes of 3-3' (bis)-Thiohydantoin with Bivalent Metal Ions

K. C. SATPATHY, T. D. MAHANA and H. P. MISHRA

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University,
Burla-768 017

Manuscript received 3 December 1979, revised 27 May 1980,
accepted 9 September 1980

THE preparation of metal chelates with N,N' -di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine has been reported by us earlier¹. 3-3' (bis)-thiohydantoin (H_2 BTHT) is a derivative of N,N' -di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine². As a part of our programme to study the fungitoxicity of sulphur donor ligands and their metal complexes, attempts were made to synthesize metal chelates with H_2 BTHT.

Experimental

3-3' (bis)-thiohydantoin (H_2 BTHT) was prepared by literature method³ (m.p. 260°). Metal complexes were prepared adopting standard procedure³. The constituent parts of each complex have been estimated by established analytical methods⁴. The i.r. spectra, electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out as reported earlier³.

Results and Discussion

A striking feature in the i.r. spectra of the component reactant, N,N' -di (thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine¹ is the appearance of a series of bands in the vicinity of 3300 cm^{-1} which arise due to the stretching vibrations of NH_2 and NH groups. Another significant band of strong intensity and of moderate width appears near 1545 cm^{-1} which arises due to NH_2 deformation. All these bands are significantly absent in the newly synthesized organic molecule and clearly imply the non-existence of either NH_2 or NH or OH groups and provide strong evidence in favour of the existence of the compound in structural form I. The S-H stretching vibrations⁵ appearing as a weak band in the ligand ~ 2460 cm^{-1} disappear in the inner complex salts.

I

In the region 3600-3200 cm^{-1} a strong and broad band appears in all the metal complexes that contain water of hydration. The high frequency band observed at 1730 cm^{-1} in the ligand attributed to $C=O$ stretching vibration undergoes a shift to a lower frequency region (40-50 cm^{-1}) in all the metal complexes³. The $C=N$ band (at 1625 cm^{-1}) on the other hand is found to shift to a higher frequency region or remains nearly unaffected.

A relatively broad band of medium intensity appears in the spectra of the ligand near about 1400 cm^{-1} which shows considerable structure and most probably arises due to CH_2 deformation and $C=S$ stretching vibrations⁶⁻⁹. In the metal complexes there appear a much sharper band at ~ 1400 cm^{-1} and an additional band of medium intensity appears near 1300 cm^{-1} . These observations indicate the shift of the ligand $C=S$ stretching vibration (observed at 1400 cm^{-1}) towards a lower frequency region, keeping the CH_2 deformation vibration unaffected and further attribute the coordination of $C=S$ group with the metal ions.

Two ligand bands at about 1350 cm^{-1} and 1250 cm^{-1} do not undergo much change in the metal complexes and probably arise due to CH_2 deformation vibrations.

The characteristic $\nu(C=S)$ in the lower frequency region^{10,11} is reported in the range 805-720 cm^{-1} . The ligand band appearing at 720 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu(C=S)$ vibration which undergoes a downward shift in all the metal complexes.

These observations logically lead us to propose the structure of the metal complexes as shown in Fig. II wherein the ligand is bonded to the metal ions in a tetrafunctional manner involving coordination of $C=O$ and $C=S$ groups and spanning towards two metal ions in *trans* structures and further forming delocalized seven-membered chelate ring.

II

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF 3-3'(bis)-THIOHYDANTOIN AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Formula	Colour	Metal % Found (Calcd)	Sulphur % Found (Calcd.)	Nitrogen % Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} in B.M. at $32 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$
1.	(H ₂ BTHT)	White		27.73 (27.83)	24.40 (24.35)	
2.	Cu(BTHT), 2H ₂ O	Green	19.24 (19.39)	19.98 (19.54)	17.02 (17.10)	1.75
3.	Ni(BTHT), H ₂ O	Light-green	19.28 (19.26)	21.23 (21.00)	18.47 (18.33)	2.46
4.	Co(BTHT), H ₂ O	Brown	19.38 (19.32)	20.98 (20.99)	18.27 (18.37)	4.31
5.	Fe(BTHT), 2.5H ₂ O	Pale green	16.96 (16.99)	19.28 (19.45)	16.98 (17.02)	5.44
6.	Mn(BTHT), 2H ₂ O	Grey	17.98 (17.16)	20.23 (20.01)	17.45 (17.51)	5.39
7.	Pd(BTHT), 3H ₂ O	Chocolate	26.92 (27.39)	16.32 (16.47)	14.60 (14.42)	Diamagnetic
8.	Cd(BTHT), 3H ₂ O	White	28.93 (28.56)	16.19 (16.23)	13.75 (13.88)	
9.	Hg(BTHT), H ₂ O	Light-yellow	44.48 (44.91)	12.95 (12.54)	14.79 (14.33)	
10.	Mg(BTHT), 4H ₂ O	White	9.32 (9.44)	19.55 (19.73)	17.02 (17.27)	

The electronic spectra of copper(II) complex show an asymmetric ligand field band in the region 14,000-17,000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to ($^2A_{1g} \approx ^2B_{2g}$) \rightarrow 2E_g and $^2B_{2g}$ transition^{1,2} under a tetragonal field. The chromophore CuS_2O_3 may be considered to have D_{2h} symmetry. Important transition is observed in the spectrum of Ni(II) complex at 16,000 cm^{-1} . This band may be assigned to $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3G_{1g}$ (F) transition under octahedral approximation. The charge transfer band has been assigned beyond 20,000 cm^{-1} . Cobalt(II) complex shows a band system in the region 16,000-20,000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $^4T_{1g}$ (F) \rightarrow $^4T_{1g}$ (P) transition in an approximately octahedral field. Paramagnetism has been noticed in the complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Mn(II). The Pd(II) complex is diamagnetic.

Cobalt(II) complex exhibits low magnetic moment. This may be due to the presence of two types of species i.e., spin-free and spin-paired ions as reported earlier^{1,3}.

High insolubility of the complexes in water and in common organic solvents point towards polymeric structure. The octahedral field may be due to out of plane coordination through S atom.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi and Sambalpur University for the award of Junior Research Fellowships to (H.P.M.) and (T.D.M.) respectively.

References

1. K. C. SATPATHY and T. D. MAHANA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1173.
2. P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY and A. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 753.
3. K. C. SATPATHY, H. P. MISHRA and T. D. MAHANA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 248.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", The English Language Book Society and Longman, Third Edition, 1969, p. 462.
5. L. J. BELLAMY, "Advances in Infrared Group Frequencies". Methuen & Co. Ltd., 11 New Fetter Lane, Ec. 4, 1968, p. 117.
6. K. SWAMINATHAN and H. IRVING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 129.
7. A. YAMAGUCHI, R. B. PENLAND, S. MIZUSHIMA, T. J. LANE, CURRAN COLUMBE and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 527.
8. R. W. OLIFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2036.
9. G. B. AITKEN, J. L. DUNCAN and G. P. MCQUILLAN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 2695.
10. M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GRAZESKOWIAK, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 396.
11. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, *Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds*, Second Edition, John Wiley & Sons, 1967.
12. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier Publishing Company, New York, 1968, p. 355.
13. K. C. SATPATHY, T. D. MAHANA and H. P. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc. (Communicated)*.